

SYNTHESIS AND DIELECTRIC CHARACTERIZATION OF BARIUM SUBSTITUTED STRONTIUM BISMUTH NIOBATE LAYERED PEROVSKITE OXIDES

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ABSTRACT

The strontium bismuth niobate, $SrBi_2Nb_2O_9$ (SBN) is a bismuth layered perovskite oxide compound with potentially useful ferroelectric properties which offer several advantages such as fatigue free, lead free, low operating voltages, relatively high Curie temperature; and most importantly, their ferroelectric properties are independent of film thickness. These materials are also important for Fe-RAM applications having large remanent polarization and low coercivity accompanied by high Curie temperature for better performance and reliable operation. Present paper describes synthesis, dielectric properties and impedance studies to reveal the important properties of barium substituted strontium bismuth niobate, $Sr_{0.85}Ba_{0.15}Bi_2Nb_2O_9$ in the system $Sr_{1-x}Ba_xBi_2Nb_2O_9$ ($x=0.15$).

KEYWORDS

Bismuth layered Aurivillius type compounds, Ferroelectrics, Space charge polarization, Impedance spectroscopy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bismuth layered Aurivillius type compounds have a general formula $[Bi_2O_2]^{2+} [A_{n-1}B_nO_{3n+1}]^{2-}$ ($n=1, 2, 3, 4$) consisting of perovskite $[A_{n-1}B_nO_{3n+1}]^{2-}$ structure sandwiched between Para-electric $[Bi_2O_2]^{2+}$ layers. Here, A can be a divalent element like Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ca^{2+} etc. and B can be Nb^{5+} , Ta^{5+} , Mo^{5+} , W^{6+} , Fe^{3+} , Ti^{4+} , V^{5+} etc [1,2,3,4]. Structurally, the Aurivillius phase is typified by fluorite-like $[Bi_2O_2]^{2+}$ interspersed between perovskite-like $[A_{n-1}B_nO_{3n+1}]^{2-}$ layers (where n represents the number of layers). The role of bismuth oxide layer in properties of these ceramics has been found to be critical [5]. The bismuth oxide layer structured ferroelectrics may become important piezoelectric ceramics because of their higher stability, higher operating temperature ($T_c = 550-650^\circ C$), and higher operating frequency. These ceramics are mainly useful for piezoelectric resonators which need to exhibit a very stable resonant frequency. In comparison with non-layered perovskite ferroelectrics such as lead zirconate titanate (PZT), bismuth layer structured ferroelectrics offer several advantages such as fatigue free, lead free, low operating voltages; and most importantly, their ferroelectric properties are independent of film thickness. For Fe-RAM applications, large remnant polarization and low coercivity accompanied by high Curie temperature are required for better performance and reliable operation. These ceramics are very sensitive to compositional variations. The properties of the layered perovskite ferroelectrics can be enhanced by addition or substitution of alternative cations. Doping at different sites modify the structure and influences properties of these materials. Aurivillius type bismuth layered materials have received a lot of attention because of their application in ferroelectric non-volatile

random access memories. [6-8]. Recently, bismuth oxide layered perovskite materials, such as $\text{SrBi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$ (SBN), $\text{SrBi}_2\text{Ta}_2\text{O}_9$ (SBT), and $\text{SrBi}_2(\text{Nb,Ta})_2\text{O}_9$ (SBTN), for Fe-RAM applications have attracted an increasing attention in the research community, because they are fatigue-free and lead-free and possess ferroelectric properties independent of film thickness [9-11]. Layered perovskite ferroelectrics, however, suffer from two drawbacks: a relatively low remanent polarization and a high processing temperature. Recently, efforts have been made to enhance the properties of layered perovskite ferroelectrics by the addition or substitution of alternative cations. For example, partial substitution of Sr^{2+} by Bi^{3+} has resulted in the most noticeable improvement of ferroelectric properties. [12-13]. In present work was undertaken with an objective to study the effect of partial substitution of strontium by barium in $\text{SrBi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$ (SBN), i.e. $\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{Ba}_x\text{Bi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$, an important bismuth layered perovskite compound. In present work, composition $\text{Sr}_{0.85}\text{Ba}_{0.15}\text{Bi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$ with $x = 0.15$ in the system $\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{Ba}_x\text{Bi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$ was prepared by solid state reaction method and resulting ceramics were characterised by their dielectric properties.

2. Experimental Details

The samples of the composition $\text{Sr}_{0.85}\text{Ba}_{0.15}\text{Bi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$ in the system $\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{Ba}_x\text{Bi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9(x=0.15)$ were prepared by conventional high temperature solid state ceramic method. In this method, the appropriate amounts of compounds of constituent ions were weighed accurately using an electronic single pan balance having accuracy 0.0001 gm. These weighed powders were transferred in to an agate mortar, mixed and grounded finely for 04 hours using acetone as mixing media to ensure effective, homogeneous mixing of all the starting powders. This homogeneous mixed and dried powder was calcined in alumina crucible at 900 °C for three hours. The calcined powder was again mixed and grounded for 02 hours with 5% solution of polyvinyl acetate as a binder. This mixed powder was used to make cylindrical pellets of diameter 12 mm and thickness in the range 2-3 mm with the help of die and hydraulic press. These prepared pellets were kept in alumina boat and heated for sintering in a programmable high temperature furnace. The binder from the pellet was first evaporated by slow heating up to 400 °C after which temperature of the furnace was gradually increased to 1000°C and sintered for 03 hours. These samples were then furnace cooled in air to room temperature. The two faces of the pellets were polished and coated with a thin layer of conducting silver paste and dried at 100°C in air. The capacitance (C), Phase angle and dielectric loss (D) was measured as a function of frequency at few selected temperature using HIOKI 352-50 LCR Hi-tester using a computer interfaced measuring cell and low temperature furnace.

Complex Impedance Spectroscopy

Generally, the impedance properties arises due to intra-grain, inter-grain and electrode processes. The motion of charge carriers could occur in a variety of ways, namely charge displacement (by long range and short range), dipole reorientation, space charge formation etc. The impedance spectroscopy enables us to evaluate the relaxation frequency of the material. The relaxation frequency of the material is only an intrinsic property of the material at a given temperature and is independent of geometrical factors of the sample. The analysis of the electrical properties (conductivity, dielectric constant, dielectric loss etc) carried out using relaxation frequency values predict reliable properties. The complex impedance of a given material can be described by the following relation: $Z^*(\omega) = Z'(\omega) + jZ''(\omega)$. Here Z' and Z'' are ascribed to real and imaginary parts of the total impedance. Recently, this technique has been successfully applied to analyze the electrical properties of ceramic materials [14-17].

3. Results and discussion

Dielectric properties

The variation of dielectric constant with temperature at different frequencies is shown in figure-1. It is observed from above plots that dielectric constant first increases with increase in temperature and attains a maximum value at temperature 50 °C. Again when temperature is increased above 50 °C , then the value of dielectric constant decreases with increases with in temperature and attains a minimum around 85°C. After that it increases rapidly with temperature. The magnitude of the peak value of dielectric constant decreases with increase in frequency and peak becomes more diffuse as a function of frequency. In higher temperature region, strong dispersion in dielectric values is observed.

The figure-2 shows the variation of dielectric loss (tan δ or D) against temperature at few selected frequencies. The plot shows that the value of dielectric loss is high at lower temperatures. It increases from room temperature and attained maximum around 50 °C similar to the trend observed in case of temperature variation of dielectric constant as shown in figure-1 and then decreases with temperature. The peak value of dielectric loss decreases with increasing frequency but peak occurs at same temperature which shows a temperature and frequency independent relaxation process occurring in the material. In case of 10 KHz, another peak appears in high temperature region.

Figure – 1: Dielectric constant versus temperature plot.

Figure - 2: Dielectric loss versus temperature plot

Figure – 3. Variation of Dielectric constant as a function of log of frequency

Figure – 4: Variation of Dielectric loss as a function of log of frequency

Figure - 3 shows the variation of the dielectric permittivity or dielectric constant with frequency for the $\text{Sr}_{0.85}\text{Ba}_{0.15}\text{Bi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$ at different temperatures. From this plot, it is clear that the permittivity decreases monotonically with increasing frequency and attains a constant value at higher frequencies. This is because, for polar materials, the initial value of the dielectric permittivity is high, but as the frequency of the field is raised the value begins to drop, which could be because the dipoles are not able to follow the field variation at higher frequencies, as well as polarization effects (space charge). The low-frequency dispersion region is attributed to charge accumulation at the electrode–electrolyte interface or in-homogeneities present in this material during preparation process at micro-level. At higher frequencies, the periodic reversal of the electric field occurs so fast that there is no excess ion diffusion in the direction of the field. Hence, the dielectric permittivity (ϵ') decreases with increasing frequency in our samples. The measured series capacitance, C_s is given by

$$C_s = C' + \frac{1}{\omega^2 R^2 C'}$$

Where C is the frequency-independent capacitance, R is the temperature-dependent resistance, and ω is $2\pi f$. The above equation predicts that C_s should decrease with increasing frequency f ,

eventually tending to a constant value C for all temperatures and at any given frequency. Since the permittivity is directly proportional to C_s , the permittivity should decrease with increasing frequency.

The figure - 4 gives the variation of dielectric loss as function of log of frequency at various temperatures. A peak appears in dielectric loss versus log f plot which shift to higher frequency with increasing temperature. These peaks indicate the transition from short range to long range mobility with decreasing frequency by hopping from one site to neighbouring sites whereas for high frequency region ions are spatially confined and can execute only localised motion.

Figure – 5: Variation of relaxation time against $1000/T$

The variation of dielectric loss against log of frequency at different temperatures of measurement as shown in figure - 4, the dielectric loss variation with frequency shows a peak with a slightly asymmetrically broadened at each temperature, the broadening increasing with increase in temperature. The asymmetric broadening of the peaks suggests the presence of electrical processes in the material with a spread of relaxation time. In a relaxation system, one can determine the most probable relaxation time (τ) from the position of the loss peak in the D versus $\log(f)$ plots according to the relation

$$\tau = 1/f$$

where f is the relaxation frequency. Figure 5 shows the variation of relaxation time $\{\ln(\tau)\}$ with $10^3/T$ (K^{-1}). It appears to follow the Arrhenius relation; $\tau = \tau_0 \exp(-E_a/kT)$, where τ_0 is the pre-exponential factor, k is the Boltzmann constant and T the absolute temperature. The value of activation energy (E_a) as calculated from the slope of $\log(\tau)$ versus $10^3/T$ curve is found to be 0.26 eV.

Figure - 6 Frequency dependence of (a) real (Z'), (b) imaginary (Z'') parts of total impedance.

Figure 6(a) presents the variation of the log of real part impedance (Z') versus log of frequency at several temperatures. From the plot it is observed that the Z' decreases slowly in the frequency range of 1.00 KHz, depending on the temperature, and continuously with an increase in frequency. Figure 6(b) shows the variation of the log of imaginary part of the impedance (Z'') as a function of log of frequency at several temperatures. It shows appearance of peaks at a characteristic frequency dependent on temperature and can be related to the type and strength of the relaxation phenomenon occurring in the material. It can be seen that the curves display broad and low intensity peaks. The peak appears to shift with change in temperature indicating distribution of relaxation times over wide range of frequency. The magnitude of Z'' maximum decreases with temperature indicating increasing loss in the sample due to resistive property of the sample. This behaviour of impedance plot arises possibly due to the presence of space charge in the material.

Figure – 7: Variation of log of imaginary part and real part of total impedance against log of frequency at several temperatures.

The real and imaginary part of the dielectric constant is plotted as a function of frequency are shown in figure-7 at few selected temperatures. It is observed from these plots that both the real and imaginary parts of dielectric constant show strong frequency dependence in lower frequency range. This is a common features of dielectrics associated with ionic conductivity contribution and is referred as the low frequency dielectric dispersion. The dispersion in ϵ'' is stonger than that in ϵ' implying that it is influenced by dc conductivity which is dominating in low frequency region due to space charge polarization. Both the curves representing log of imaginary and real parts of dielectric constant intersects each other when plotted against log of frequency. The frequency at which they intersect each other decreases as one goes away from temperature at which dielectric peak occurs in dielectric constant versus temperature plot. When temperature is well away from this peak temperature, they do not intersect each other. The high value of ϵ' and

ϵ'' in low frequency region shows the effect of space charge polarization and conducting ion motion.

Figure – 8: The variation of Z'' against Z' at various temperatures.

Figure -8 shows the impedance plot (Z'' versus Z') at eight different temperature. The impedance plot at temperature 50 °C shows that there is a depressed semicircle in high frequency range. When the temperature increases from 50 °C, a second semicircle start appearing in low frequency region. The above plots composed of two semicircle, a small semicircle at high frequency indicates the effect of grain and large semicircle at low frequency indicates the of grain boundary effect. The intercept of of the semicircle on real axis gives the resistance of the grain (R_b) and grain boundary (R_{gb}) of the corresponding component contributing towards the impedance of the sample. It is also observed that resistance (grain) corresponding to first semicircle continuously decreasing with increase in temperature. The same trend is observed at higher temperature also.

The observed depressed semicircle are in high frequency region indicates that there is distribution of relaxation times in the material. This is also indicative of the presence of both localised and non localised conduction process in the material.

The observed dielectric properties of the material can be explain using impedance data. As temperature increase the difference in resistance grain and grain boundary increases which cause large conductivity difference in material at microlevels. This difference in conductivity gives rise to space charge at microlevels, hence large value of dielectric constant at high temperature is observed in the material. The strong frequency dependence of dielectric properties is due to formation of space charge.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors are thankful to Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur and one of us (HST) is thankful to University grant Commission, New Delhi for financial assistance.

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